

automatically disintegrated and mixed with the soil within a week. No manual mixing was necessary and there was no sign of injury to the rice crop.

The legume increased rice germination by 21% under the crust and affected the lateritic upland situation. Twenty-day-old sesbania bearing 7 to 17 nodules/plant contributed 4.3-6.3 t green manure/ha.

Grain yield increased significantly (see table). The yield with sesbania alone equaled yield with 40 kg N/ha. □

Effects of nitrogen and sesbania on number of nodules, green matter from sesbania, plant population, and rice yield. Orissa, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Sesbania nodules/plant ^a (no.)	Sesbania green matter incorporated (t/ha) ^a	Rice plants/m ²		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Without sesbania	With sesbania	Without sesbania	With sesbania
0	6.8	4.3	274	326	1.1	1.4
20	12.8	4.8	277	241	1.2	1.5
30	13.2	5.6	218	345	1.3	1.5
40	15.6	5.8	252	313	1.5	1.8
50	17.0	6.3	280	359	1.6	2.1
Mean	13.10	5.4	260	316	1.3	1.6
CD (0.05)						0.2

^aTreatments had received 50% N at time of data collection.

Split application of slow-release urea

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We studied the comparative efficiency and time of application of slow-release urea materials such as neem cake-coated urea (NCCU, 20% neem cake powder), coal tar-coated urea (CTCU, 1% coal tar), urea supergranule (USG, 1-g size), and prilled urea (PU) in 2 soil types.

ADT36 (110 d, Jun-Sep 1984) and IR20 (135 d, Sep 1984-Feb 1985) were tested in the clayey loam soils of Aduthurai (silty clay to clay, Vertisol, clay 40% low in N) where 2 rice crops are usually grown. IR20 (medium duration, Jul-Dec 1984) was tested in the sandy loam soils of Pattukottai (sandy loam, Alfisol, clay 12.0% low in N). The recommended NPK of 75.0-

Effect of split application of slow-release urea on yield. India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	Clay soil		Sandy loam soil
	Crop 1	Crop 2	
<i>Source</i>			
NCCU	4.6	4.6	4.6
CTCU	4.8	4.7	4.7
USG	5.0	4.7	5.0
PU	4.4	4.5	4.7
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2
<i>Time of application</i>			
Single basal (slow-release urea)	4.5	4.6	4.5
Single basal (50% slow-release + 50% PU)	4.5	4.5	4.5
Split application ^a (slow-release urea)	5.0	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal PU + topdressed slow-release urea)	4.9	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal slow-release + topdressed PU)	4.6	4.8	4.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2

^aSplit application = 50% N before planting, 50% N at maximum tillering.

37.5-37.5 kg/ha for the 110-d variety and 100-50-50 kg/ha for the 135-d variety were applied.

USG gave significantly higher yields than PU in both soil types (see table).

Yields with NCCU and CTCU only equaled that with PU. Split application of slow-release urea gave higher yields than single basal in both soils. □

Effect of soil moisture regime and straw incorporation on root growth and yield of rice

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We conducted a lysimeter experiment with rice variety PR106 on a calcareous sandy loam soil (Typic

Ustochrept). Air-dried soil was passed through a 2-mm sieve and used to fill iron barrels 1 m high with 50-cm internal diameter. The treatments, replicated 3 times, were combinations of 3 levels of straw incorporation (no straw, 1% straw, and 2% straw) and 3 soil moisture regimes (field capacity, saturation, and submergence). Straw was chopped into 2- to 4-cm pieces and mixed into the top 15 cm of soil.

The soil moisture treatments were imposed after 3 wk of continuous submergence following transplanting. To attain field capacity, 4-6 cm water was applied 24 h after infiltration of water previously applied. Saturation was 0-1.5 cm ponded water; submergence was 4-6 cm ponded water. Fertilizer was applied at 150 kg N and 13 kg P/ha.

Depth of roots was determined at